

NATURE OF THE TOURISM INDUSTRY

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Abstract. *In this article, the tourist industry (industry) is a coordinated system that provides tourism services, work and goods necessary for the consumption of tourists in the process of tourism and its specific features. Also, the author gives recommendations that the development of mass tourism in the world will lead to such intensive development of the tourism industry and economic sectors, religion and culture, and the education system.*

Key words: *tourism, tourist, tourism industry, international-tourism tourist-excursion, guide-interpreter.*

Introduction Today, there are many definitions of the concept of "tourism industry", and the most reliable and perfect of such definitions was given by the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development. As recognized at this conference, the tourism industry consists of a collection of various activities of all tourist organizations aimed at creating tourist products to meet the needs of tourists. Over the years, there have been many studies to define the content and essence of this definition and to describe the components of the tourism industry.

However, researchers and practitioners who tried to do this faced various difficulties and obstacles. The main reason for the occurrence of such difficulties is the close connection of the tourism industry with other sectors of the economy. Industry and agriculture, construction and trade sectors participate as a single, separate structure in meeting the broad needs of tourism. Therefore, it is very difficult to sharply demarcate the tourism industry from other industries.

According to the US Department of Commerce, 24 branches of the country's economy are involved in the field of visitor services. In this regard, it is very difficult to set a clear limit on the tourism sector and separate it from the sectors. The development of mass tourism in the world has led to the intensive development of the tourism industry and the interconnected branches of the economy, religion and culture, and the education system. Based on these conditions, it can be said that the tourism industry includes hotels and other means of accommodation, transportation services, public catering facilities, places and facilities for entertainment, educational, medical, health, sports, religious. - is a set of organizations that implement ceremonial, business and other purposes, tourism operators and tourism agencies, as well as offer tourist-excursion and guide-interpreting services. The concept of tourism industry is defined in the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Tourism" as follows: Tourism industry - various entities of tourism activity that provide services to tourists (hotels, tourist complexes, campsites, motels, boarding houses, public catering, transport companies, culture, sports facilities, etc.) complex. At the current stage of development, regardless of the social structure of the country or the tourist center, there are several different types of enterprises that carry out tourist activities in the tourism industry, such as: tour operators and tourist agencies that organize tourism. In addition, they include tourist transportation, hotels and other enterprises of the accommodation system, catering, attractions and entertainment, as well as banking institutions, insurance services, etc. Special types of tourism can include medical institutions, institutions of

the educational system, sports and other institutions that correspond to the goals of a specific tourist product. All these organizations complement each other harmoniously and provide all the services necessary for the consumer and at a sufficient level of assortment. The development of tourism, the domestic economy of each country opportunity, integration of all economic sectors

is important. This, in turn, affects the population increases mobility and develops service tourism. Usually the life of the people in economically developed countries

due to the slightly higher level of prosperity, tourism movement has a mass character. That is the main reason for this the amount of monthly salary of workers, which they receive during their holidays a lot of vacation money, a lot of pension money for pensioners is characterized by being Socio-demographic factors are unique features. Increase in the population for the development of tourism,

it is mainly affected by the increase in the urban population. According to psychologists, the town is a form of life, mental a lot of work, extreme industrialization, loss of wild nature increases the desire of the city's residents for tourism. Besides that increase in average life expectancy and fertility among the population a relative decrease is observed. Hence tourism take into account the above circumstances when organizing the industry should be taken. That is, additional medical services, diet meals, focus on increasing cultural ceremonies and excursions is considered important. All the factors mentioned above have their influence on the formation and development of tourism. Therefore, the analysis of these factors, their determining which ones are of primary importance, in turn, leading to the effective use of tourist resources will come.

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